

SAGE: a Semantic Annotator for knowledge Graph Exploration

Dutta, Biswanath
Das, Puranjani

DRTC, Indian Statistical Institute, India | bisu@drtc.isibang.ac.in
DRTC, Indian Statistical Institute, India | puranjanidas02@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

SAGE (a Semantic Annotator for knowledge Graph Exploration) is a “Thing” annotation system. Here, “Thing” refers to any concept, named individuals (aka entities), entity relations, and attributes. The system is primarily built based on the idea of “string to thing” where the “string” is any given text (e.g., abstract of an article) as input by the user. For annotation, the system utilizes the knowledge graph(s). SAGE can be used by anyone for annotating Things and for their exploitation on the Web. The annotation of things is done through exact and partial matches. For the exact matches, the system makes explicit the name of the knowledge graphs it is sourced from. It also shows the type hierarchies for the matched named entities. The system is designed following the rule-based approach. In the current work, we describe the SAGE annotation system along with its features and various usage, and the experimental results.

KEYWORDS

Semantic annotation, thing annotation, entity annotation, knowledge graph exploration, thing spotting, management

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge Graph (KG), a manifestation of an intelligent Web of data, informed by an ontology and their related applications, have been prominent for quite some time now. KG is seen as data (which can be queried), as a graph (which can be analyzed as a network of data), and as a knowledge base (from where new facts can be inferred) (Blumaumer & Kiryakov, n.d.). Over time, many knowledge graphs have been built across various domains in academia (e.g., CODO KG (Dutta & DeBellis, 2020; DeBellis & Dutta, 2021), DTO (Lin et al., 2017), BAO (BioAssay Ontology, n.d.), DRON (Hogan et al., 2017) and in the industry (e.g., google knowledge graph (Google Knowledge Graph, n.d.)).

As observed in the literature, the KGs have various uses. They are explored through different means and for various purposes. For example, for developing Question-Answer (Q/A) systems (Huang et al., 2021) like WolframAlpha (Wolfram/Alpha, n.d.), for semantic search and retrieval purposes (e.g., Google search engine’s results ‘infobox’ that appears next to the search results), for information integration (Dbpedia Spotlight, n.d.), for data visualization and exploration (e.g., CovidGraph (CovidGraph, n.d.)). The KGs are also explored for semantic annotation purposes. One such example is DBpedia Spotlight (Mendes et al., 2011). It automatically annotates the DBpedia resources mentioned in the text. The DBpedia Spotlight (DBS) annotates the entities against the selected resource types (e.g., place, person, organization, and event). The DBS is limited to named entity annotation only. It does not annotate the concepts, entity relations, and attributes. Also, the DBS misses the entities that are not captured and defined as resources within the DBpedia. Besides, DBS does not explicitly indicate the entities that are not annotated. We have to manually identify the missing entities. FICLONE is an annotation tool that primarily aimed to improve the DBS in terms of Named Entity Recognition (NER) and collective disambiguation (Chabchoub et al., 2018). The tool is dependent on DBS to annotate the text. The annotations returned by DBS are used directly for annotation. So, the FICLONE performance and accuracy are dependent on DBS and DBpedia resources.

In this work, we design and develop a brand-new semantic annotation system, namely SAGE (a Semantic Annotator for knowledge Graph Exploration), and can be downloaded from <https://tinyurl.com/y4yjc3y2>. Here, “Thing” refers to any resources including entities (i.e., the named entities), concepts (aka classes), and properties, such as relations (aka object properties) and attributes (aka data properties). The tool is motivated primarily by DBS and other general-purpose text annotation systems, such as Doccano (Doccano · GitHub, n.d.), BRAT (Brat Rapid Annotation Tool, n.d.), etc. SAGE follows the idea of “strings to things.” The system annotates the KG things mentioned in the text as strings. It identifies and labels strings in a text corpus with things (the elements that are defined with URIs) found in the knowledge graph. In a knowledge graph, each thing has a URI. SAGE binds the URIs of the things in the knowledge graphs to the phrases present in the text. So, that the thing from the user-given text is annotated, linked, negotiated, and explored on the Web. The SAGE annotates things following two approaches - exact matching and partial matching. Besides, in case of the unavailability of resources in the KG for the entities mentioned in the text, the system identifies them as unmatched entities and presents them along with their part of speeches (POS). SAGE is a domain-independent tool hence any KG, or ontologies can be used to form its knowledge base. Also, multiple numbers of KGs at a time can be added to its knowledge base for exploration. The system design architecture along

with its various features are discussed in the system design section. The evaluation of SAGE yields impressive results provided in the results and evaluation section.

The main contributions of this work are: (1) the design and develop a desktop application called SAGE for "Thing" annotation; (2) the application provides GUI for uploading knowledge graphs, annotation, and exploration of things from the knowledge graph with ease; and (3) the application reduces the technological complexity of exploration of knowledge graphs which usually demand the user's technological expertise.

SYSTEM DESIGN

In this section, we describe the SAGE architecture and its various features.

System Architecture

As shown in Figure 1, SAGE is designed to take 2 types of inputs (1) Text to be annotated and (2) KGs to be explored. The input text is a string from which the things will be identified based on the KGs by the SAGE matcher. As stated above (see Introduction), the system identifies 2 kinds of matches: exact (terms from the input text which exist as things in the KGs) and partial (terms from the input text which do not exist as things in the KGs, but as a part of other things). These matches are described in the next section. The matches found can be classes, instances, data, and object properties. Various forms of the terms (singular and plural) found in the KGs are matched against the given string input. Following the exact matches found, the system links them with their respective URIs. For the matched named entities, the system gives its type information. The system also enlists the exact-matched things to be used in pre-defined queries, which lets the user explore the tuples associated with the things. In the case of partial matches, the things in the KG which contain terms from input text are enlisted and linked to their URIs. The hyperlinked things obtained from exact and partial matches, allow the users to learn more about them from their descriptions on the web. The system spots the unmatched terms from the input and categorises them according to their parts of speech (detailed below). Figure 1 shows the overall architecture of SAGE.

Figure 1. Software Architecture of SAGE

Features

Following are the primary features of SAGE: (1) exploration of KGs without writing a query (2) identification of missing things in a KG (3) estimation of coverage of KGs (4) KG statistics.

Exploration of KG

SAGE allows the user to explore the things in KGs against scholarly literature. The user can paste a text excerpt of domain literature and the tool annotates the things that it recognizes from the KG. The tool links these things with their URI, allowing the user to explore them from the source. The users do not need any query-building knowledge or coding skills for exploring the things in the KG through SAGE. The tool facilitates the users to upload their own KG in RDF/XML format. Thereby, enabling the user to explore the KG of their choice. Multiple KGs can be selected at a time for exploration against domain literature.

a) Exact Match- The tool annotates the exact matched things within the text. Example: in Figure 2, the terms *pneumonia*, *coronavirus*, *diseases*, etc. are found in the text excerpt taken from a paper (Lotfi et al., 2020) against CODO (DeBellis & Dutta, 2021) and CIDO (He et al., 2020) ontologies. These terms are linked to their URIs and will lead to their description on the web upon being clicked. SAGE also presents a list of those things indicating their source KGs. As the tool allows the selection of multiple KGs for annotation, it gets difficult to track the source of things from where they are being annotated. Additionally, there are terms that occur in multiple KGs. Therefore, the annotator provides a separate space to enlist all the exact matched terms indicating their source KG. For example, as shown in the figure, the things like *coronavirus*, *disease*, *cases*, etc. are annotated indicating their source ontology CODO, CIDO, or OBO, etc. in parenthesis.

b) Partial Match- SAGE also provides an annotated list of partially matched things, in order to provide the user with contextually relevant resources. In continuation of the example shown in Figure 2, terms like *new*, *preventive*, and *health* from the text are found as parts of terms in CODO. Figure 3(a) shows, *health* is found in *Dedicated Covid Health Centre (DCHC)*, *virus* is found in *contracted virus from*, etc. It is worth mentioning that, SAGE also presents the type information of the exact matched entities from the KGs, whenever it is available. For example, *COVID-19* is a named entity that was found in the exact match from CODO as shown in Figure 2. Figure 3(b) shows that *COVID-19* is a type of *Coronavirus disease*.

Figure 2. Main window, with exact matches

Partial Matches

coronavirus: [Coronavirus infection](#)
 health: [Dedicated Covid Health Centre \(DCHC\)](#)
 released: [released on](#)
 virus: [contracted virus from](#)
 acute: [Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome \(ARDS\)](#)
 respiratory: [Upper Respiratory Tract Infection](#), [Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome \(ARDS\)](#)
 syndrome: [Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome \(ARDS\)](#)

Figure 3. (a) Snippet of Partial Matches

Coronavirus infection
 COVID-19
 Symptom
 sneezing

(b) Exact matched entity types

c) Predefined Query- Apart from annotating and exploring things on the web as described above, SPARQL *select* queries are defined on exact matches, which returns all the tuples associated with the matched things. These queries are defined for each matched entity and the user does not have to write them. Fig 4, shows the query interface and the results. The defined queries are: Class: *select ?s ?p where {?s ?p <term URI>}*, Property: *select ?s ?o where {?s <term URI> ?o}* and Instance: *select ?p ?o where { <term URI> ?p ?o}*.

Figure 4. Predefined query results

Identification of missing things in a KG

As observed (see Figure 2), the things like *epidemic*, *etiology* remain unannotated, even though the KG used as a knowledge resource in the current study is a COVID-19-related KG. These terms could be a valuable addition to the COVID-19-related KGs. The SAGE spots and lists the terms missing from the KGs along with their Parts-of-Speech (POS). For this purpose, the Stanford POS tagger is used. Originally, Stanford POS tagger categorises the terms into 36 POS categories, for example, CC, VBG, VBZ, NNP, NNPS, TO, etc. (*Penn Parts-of-speech, n.d.*). However, SAGE drops some of the categories, especially those that are not useful from the KG perspective (e.g., DT, TO, WRB, CC, etc.), and also regroups some of the categories (e.g., NN, NNP, VBG, JJ, RB, etc.) into six categories: Nouns, Proper Nouns, Verbs, Adjectives, Gerunds, and Adverbs. Figure 5 presents a list based on the spotted missing terms for the example shown in Figure 2. This feature is extremely helpful in the updating and maintenance of an ontology.

Estimation of coverage of KG

The user can see the coverage of each KG against the uploaded domain literature in terms of the exact match found. For example, as indicated in Figure 6, the exact match things found from the text against the CODO ontology is 1.581%. If multiple KGs are selected for annotation purposes, the user can even compare the coverage of the KGs. This feature of SAGE is very useful, specifically for ontology engineers. This enables them to visualize the state of their KG compared to other KGs within a domain. Equation 1 provides the coverage calculation formula. The system mentions the number of terms matched and the length of the original input after dropping the stop words (see Figure 6).

$$coverage = \frac{no.of\ exactly\ matched\ things\ in\ text\ from\ KG}{total\ number\ of\ things\ in\ KG} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (Equation\ 1)$$

KG statistics

As mentioned above, the user can upload the KGs of his choice using the GUI. These KGs are displayed in the right-hand panel of the main window as shown in Figure 2. Along with the names of these KGs, SAGE also displays the number of things in the KGs. This helps the user check the overall coverage of various KGs and compare them. As depicted in Figure 2, CIDO, CODO, and Food ontologies consist of 11598, 506, and 35166 things, respectively.

Parts of Speech for Things not found in Knowledge Base (NOUN) delay, outbreak, novel, lungs, growth, "", end, world, lockdown, patients, emergent transmission, investigation, diseases, market, etiology, "", measures, spread, bats, droplets, c pandemic, model, committee, individuals, isolation, epidemic, coughing, respiratory, onset, (PROPER NOUN) who, coronavirus, study, human, health, wuhan, "", csg, world, commissi (VERB) examined, proposed, reported, concluded, were, achieved, have, been, taken, pred followed, released, caused, vns, (ADJECTIVE) preventive, human-to-human, severe, more, upper, causative, rapid, essential respiratory, new, much, further, acute, other,

Figure 5. Unmatched terms with their POS

Things found- 8 in 189 words (stopwords excluded). Coverage of Cido is 0.06897740989825832

Things found- 8 in 189 words (stopwords excluded). Coverage of codo_2 is 1.5810276679841897

Figure 6. Coverage of ontologies CIDO and CODO

RESULT AND EVALUATION

a) Feature comparison: In Table 1, we compare the features of DBS with SAGE. The default knowledge base supported by DBS is not customizable. Whereas, the customization of KG is supported by SAGE, and this makes this tool more domain-friendly. SAGE annotates concepts, named entities, relations, and attributes, whereas DBS only annotates the named entities. SAGE provides partial matching which enables the discovery of things in context, whereas DBS does not support partial matching. Besides, SAGE facilitates KG maintenance by spotting the potential missing terms and their POS categories. It also enables the comparison of KGs in terms of their domain coverage. SAGE automatically builds queries based on annotated terms, which eventually enables the retrieval of things from the knowledge base. These are some of the additional features that make SAGE superior to DBS.

Features Annotator	Annotation (exact things)	Partial Matches	Entity Type	Customize KB	Missing Terms	KG coverage	KG statistics	Predefined Query
DBS	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	X	X
SAGE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1. Comparison of features of DBS with SAGE

b) Response time: For measuring the time performance of SAGE, we use three existing ontologies, namely CODO (O_1), CIDO (O_2), and FoodOn (O_3), and two domain-specific literature (see Table 2) as input text source for the study. CODO and CIDO are Covid-19 ontologies and FoodOn (Lange et al., 2007) is a food ontology. We can see from Table 2, the exact match response time of SAGE is directly proportional to the length of the input text. For example, the response time for O_1 is 0.39 seconds (rounded to two decimal points) for 500 words, 0.68 seconds for 1000 words, and 1.27 seconds for 2000 words. A similar pattern is observed for O_2 and O_3 . This is also to be noted that the response time is greater when the size of the ontology is greater. As can be seen, for a 500-word input text, the response time for O_2 and O_3 consisting of 11598 and 35166 things, respectively is higher compared to the O_1 which consists of a relatively less number of things i.e., 506.

Text Source	Input Text Length	Text Length (ARS)	Time (in secs) for O_1 (506)	Text Length (ARS)	Time (in secs) for O_2 (11598)	Text Length (ARS)	Time (in secs) for O_3 (35166)
(Lotfi et al., 2020)	500	310	0.390616	310	17.92897	320	51.63919
	1000	619	0.687281	619	29.03405	719	87.90444
(Kammoun et al., 2017)	2000	1237	1.265422	1237	51.81634	1362	159.0386

Table 2. Evaluation of time with respect to the length of input text. ARS- After Removing Stop words

Note: For O_3 , as the domain is different from O_1 and O_2 , a different sample text is taken as shown in column one. Hence, a different length of words is obtained after dropping the stop words.

CONCLUSION

The current work is focused on designing and developing a tool, namely SAGE to exploit knowledge graphs for thing annotation. It annotates the KG resources mentioned in the text. Its GUI enables anyone to explore things in KG easily. It also supports the addition of multiple KGs of the user's choice in its knowledge base. The advantage of using SAGE annotation is that it not only annotates the named entities but also the concepts, entity relations, and attributes. The tool provides primarily two kinds of annotations: based on complete matching and partial matching. The partial annotation is useful as it annotates the contextually-relevant resources. The other advantage of this tool is that the entities mentioned in the text but not defined as a resource in the knowledge base of the system do not completely go unnoticed. The system parses those entities through the POS system and displays them. This is useful from the perspective of further enrichment of the ontology or the KG. The domain experts and ontology engineers may find them interesting to add to the existing KG. Further, the tool may also be used to compare the KGs coverage. As discussed, the system's unmatched terms pane indicates and enlists the missing resources in the KG. In the future, we plan to develop a GUI to enable the knowledge engineers to add the missing things to the KG directly from the SAGE's unmatched terms result interface. For now, SAGE only supports RDF-XML formatted KGs as input, we plan to expand it to other serialization.

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REFERENCES

- BioAssay Ontology*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 13, 2022, from <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/BAO>
- Blumaumer, A., & Kiryakov, A. (n.d.). *Knowledge Graphs: 5 Use Cases and 10 Steps to Get There - Ontotext*. Retrieved December 13, 2022, from <https://www.ontotext.com/knowledgehub/webinars/knowledge-graphs-5-use-cases-and-10-steps-to-get-there/>
- brat rapid annotation tool: online environment for collaborative text annotation*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 13, 2022, from <https://brat.nlplab.org/>
- Chabchoub, M., Gagnon, M., Web, A. Z.-O. J. of S., & 2018, U. (2018). FICLONE: improving DBpedia spotlight using named entity recognition and collective disambiguation. *Open Journal Semantic Web*, 5(1), 12–28.
- CovidGraph*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 13, 2022, from <https://healthecco.org/covidgraph/>
- Dbpedia Spotlight*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 13, 2022, from <https://www.dbpedia.org/about/>
- Dutta, B. & DeBellis, M. (2020). CODO: an ontology for collection and analysis of COVID-19 data. In Proceedings of 12th International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Ontology Development (KEOD), 2-4 November 2020, Lisboa, Portugal, Vol. 2, pp. 76-85. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0010112500760085>
- DeBellis, M., & Dutta, B. (2021). The Covid-19 CODO Development Process: an Agile Approach to Knowledge Graph Development. *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, 1459 CCIS, 153–168. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-91305-2_12/COVER
- doccano · GitHub*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 13, 2022, from <https://github.com/doccano>
- Google Knowledge Graph*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 13, 2022, from <https://developers.google.com/knowledge-graph>
- Penn part-of-speech tags* (n.d.) Retrieved December 13, 2022, from <https://cs.nyu.edu/~grishman/jet/guide/PennPOS.html>
- He, Y., Yu, H., Ong, E., Wang, Y., Liu, Y., Data, A. H.-S., & 2020, U. (2020). CIDO, a community-based ontology for coronavirus disease knowledge and data integration, sharing, and analysis. *Scientific Data*, 7(181). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0523-6>
- Hogan, W. R., Hanna, J., Hicks, A., Amirova, S., Bramblett, B., Diller, M., Enderez, R., Modzelewski, T., Vasconcelos, M., & Delcher, C. (2017). Therapeutic indications and other use-case-driven updates in the drug ontology: Anti-malarials, anti-hypertensives, opioid analgesics, and a large term request. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13326-017-0121-5>
- Huang, X., Zhang, J., Xu, Z., Ou, L., Science, J. T.-P. C., & 2021, U. (2021). A knowledge graph based question answering method for medical domain. *PeerJ Computer Science*, 7. <https://peerj.com/articles/cs-667/>
- Lin, Y., Mehta, S., Küçük-McGinty, H., Turner, J. P., Vidovic, D., Forlin, M., Koletti, A., Nguyen, D. T., Jensen, L. J., Guha, R., Mathias, S. L., Ursu, O., Stathias, V., Duan, J., Nabizadeh, N., Chung, C., Mader, C., Visser, U., Yang, J. J., ... Schürer, S. C. (2017). Drug target ontology to classify and integrate drug discovery data. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13326-017-0161-X>
- Lotfi, M., Hamblin, M., Acta, N. R.-C. chimica, & 2020, U. (2020). COVID-19: Transmission, prevention, and potential therapeutic opportunities. *Clinica Chimica Acta*, 508, 254–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cca.2020.05.044>
- Mendes, P. N., Jakob, M., García-Silva, A., & Bizer, C. (2011). DBpedia spotlight: Shedding light on the web of documents. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2063518.2063519>
- Wolfram|Alpha*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 13, 2022, from <https://www.wolframalpha.com/>
- Lange, M.C., Lemay, D.G. and German, J.B. (2007). A multi-ontology framework to guide agriculture and food towards diet and health. *J. Sci. Food Agric*, 87, 1427-1434. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.2832>
- Kammoun, K., Chaker, H., Mahfoudh, H., Makhlof, N., Jarraya, F., & Hachicha, J. (2017). Diet in chronic kidney disease in a Mediterranean African country. *BMC nephrology*, 18(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12882-017-0448-2>